

A GLINT ON CANCER DIAGNOSIS: PAFOLACIANINE

Chaitali Pinaki Dhar, Akansha Thakur, Mahesh NM*

Department of Pharmacy Practice, KLE College of Pharmacy, Bengaluru, India

ABSTRACT

Pafolacianine (PFN) is an imaging agent for the diagnosis of ovarian and lung cancer in the human body. PFN binds specifically to folate receptor alpha (FR α), a membrane-bound glycoprotein receptor, upregulated more in the ovarian and lung cancer cells. It has shown rapid onset of action with better efficacy and safety profile while diagnosing ovarian and lung cancer cells. In view of these facts, the complete profile of PFN is reviewed to understand its advantages and limitations while using PFN therapeutically for the diagnosis of patients with ovarian and lung cancer.

CHEMICAL PROPERTIES

Pafolacianine (PFN) is an agent used for optical imaging of cancer foci in the human body. It is used for the diagnosis of cancer, especially ovarian cancer. Chemically, it is a tetrasodium salt known as Pafolacianine sodium. The IUPAC name of PFN sodium is (S)-2-(4-(((2-amino 4-oxo-3,4-dihydropteridin-6-yl) methyl) amino) benzamido)-3-(4-(((E)-2-((E)-2-(3,3-dimethyl-5-sulfonato-1-(4-sulfonatobutyl)-3H-indol-1-ium-2-yl) vinyl)-6-((E)-2-(3,3-dimethyl-5-sulfonato-1-(4-sulfonatobutyl) indolin-2-ylidene) ethylidene) cyclohex-1-en-1-yl) oxy) phenyl) propanoate hydrate tetrasodium. Its molecular formula is C₆₁H₆₃N₉Na₄O₁₇S₄ and its molar mass is 1414.42 g/mol^[1].

Fig. 1: Chemical Structure of Pafolacianine Sodium

The melting point of PFN is 88-94°C^[2]. It is a solid powder and soluble in dimethyl sulfoxide^[6]. PFN absorbs light in the near-infrared spectrum in a range of 760-785 nm. When excited, PFN shows fluorescence in a range of 790-815 nm^[2].

PHARMACOLOGY

Mechanism of Action

Pafolacianine binds specifically to folate receptor alpha (FR α), a membrane-bound glycoprotein receptor^[6]. FR α receptor^[11] is expressed in organs such as the ovaries and lungs. The FR α receptor is upregulated in various cancer conditions such as ovarian cancer, lung cancer, breast cancer, and gastric cancer. The FR α receptor is bound to the glycosylphosphatidylinositol pathway, which occurs in epithelial cells^[3]. PFN targets FR α receptors in positive cancer cells with an affinity of ~1 nM^[26] and gets internalized by receptor-mediated endocytosis, thereby accumulating in FR α -expressing malignant lesions^[4]. It is a folate analog conjugated to a fluorescent dye in the near-infrared, thus aiding optical imaging during surgery by absorbing light in the near-infrared and emitting fluorescence^[5].

Preclinical Studies: Pafolacianine was administered intravenously to pregnant rats during the organogenesis phase at the following doses: 0.015, 0.15, and 1.5 mg/kg/day, which was equivalent

to human doses of 0.002, 0.024, and 0.242 mg/kg/day, from gestational day 6 to day 17. There was no significant drug-related toxicity (No Adverse Effect Level at 1.5 mg/kg/day). PFN was administered intravenously to pregnant rabbits at the following doses: 0.3, 1, and 3 mg/kg/day administered from gestational day 7 to day 20, which was equivalent to human doses of 0.097, 0.323, and 0.968 mg/kg/day. There was no significant adverse effect at the level of 3 mg/kg/day^[1]. These reports suggest that the adverse effects especially on maternal and embryo foetal development are not likely to occur in mammalian species such as rats and rabbits when PFN was administered at human equivalent doses mentioned above. However, the preclinical toxicity studies are limited^[1]. The effectiveness of detecting pituitary cancer was studied using mouse pituitary tumor cell line alphaT3-1 as a model to study the biological significance of FR α and its mutant FR67. The results showed that tumor cells overexpressing FR α retain and internalize folate and any fluorescently labeled folate conjugate^[1]. This result suggests that a similar kind of study can be possible in human beings.

Clinical Studies: The efficacy and safety of PFN were evaluated in the previous clinical studies. These studies were carried out in patients who were suffering from various types of cancer. The outcome of those studies is mentioned as follows.

Ovarian Cancer

The efficacy and safety of PFN was studied in phase I to III clinical trials. In Phase I, 12 patients with ovarian cancer were administered a dose of 0.0125 mg/kg to detect malignant lesions with high specificity and sensitivity^[4]. It was found that surgeons were able to detect 29% of all the resected tumours that would have been missed by the naked eye. It was proved that PFN improves the surgeon's ability to detect malignant lesions by more than two fold, and its pharmacokinetic behavior enabled surgeons to detect malignant lesions for at least six

hours after administration of the drug. Some patients reported mild hypersensitivity reactions that were easily manageable^[4]. The disadvantage of PFN is the higher number of false positive lesions due to activated macrophages with folate receptor β and non-cancerous epithelial cells in the uterus and fallopian tube which express FR α ^[4,24]. In Phase II, 44 patients were evaluated for safety and 29 patients for efficacy. The sensitivity to detect ovarian cancer was estimated to be 97.97% and the positive predictive value was 94.93%. According to the data, at least one additional metastatic lesion was detected in 48.3% of patients by use of PFN. However, adverse effects such as abdominal pain, vomiting, nausea, and infusion reactions occurred in 8 patients^[7,25]. It was concluded that PFN was safe and effective in the phase II studies and deserves phase III evaluation. In Phase III, PFN was administered to 150 patients, of whom 109 were fully evaluated. The accuracy of PFN was demonstrated by a sensitivity of 83%. Complete resection

was achieved in 4%. However, a false-positive rate of 32.7% was noted, and the most common adverse effects were nausea (18.0%), vomiting (5.3%), and abdominal pain (4.7%). The most commonly reported adverse events were infusion-induced reactions (96%), which were mild to moderate but resolved within one day in 89% of the cases. No serious adverse drug reactions or deaths were reported [8,26]. Consequently, FDA approval of PFN was a bright spot in ovarian cancer staging and resection of malignant lesions. It has been shown to decrease recurrence rates and thus improve treatment outcomes in women with ovarian cancer.

Lung Cancer

The efficacy and safety of PFN in lung cancer were studied in phase I to III clinical trials. In the phase I clinical trial, the investigators conducted a trial in 50 patients with lung cancer. The investigators had found out excellent sensitivity and specificity with only grade 1 side effects (allergic reaction). The side effects were reversed when the injection was halted. The false positive detection rate was found to be extremely low [21]. In Phase II, the patients with lung cancer were scheduled to undergo endoscopic or thoracic surgery. Patients were infused with

PFN two to three hours prior to surgery [22]. In phase III, the safety and efficacy of PFN were evaluated in this clinical trial involving 140 patients with known or suspected lung cancer. Patients were administered with intravenous infusion of 0.025mg/kg PFN between one and 24 hours before surgery. Among these patients, 24% of patients had at least one cancerous lesion identified that had not been observed using standard visual or tactile inspection. The most common adverse events with PFN were infusion-related reactions, which included nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, flushing, dyspepsia, chest discomfort, itching, and hypersensitivity [23].

Pharmacokinetics

Absorption: PFN is administered intravenously. The C_{max} was reported to be 59.1 ± 5.94 ng/ml and the AUC_{inf} was reported to be 63.6 ± 12.6 ng.hr/ml on a single IV infusion [1].

Distribution: The mean volume of distribution was reported to be 17.1 ± 5.99 L with intravenous infusion. Plasma protein binding was reported to be 93.7%. No notable partitioning into red blood cells has been observed [1].

Metabolism: The information on the metabolism of PFN is yet to be clear as some reports suggest that it is not metabolized by cytochrome P450 (CYP) enzymes [1].

Elimination: Elimination half-life is 0.44 ± 0.23 hours and mean plasma clearance is 28.6 ± 4.97 L/hr. After a single intravenous infusion, approximately 35% of the dose is recovered in the urine and 19.1% in the feces after approximately 3-5 weeks [1].

No clinically significant differences in the pharmacokinetics of PFN were reported based on the age (18 – 89 years), body weight (41.6 – 133.6 kg), and mild to moderate renal impairment (creatinine clearance [CLCr] 30 to 89 mL/min) or hepatic impairment (total bilirubin < 3 upper limit normal [ULN] and aspartate transferase [AST] > ULN). However, the effect of severe renal impairment (CLCr < 30 mL/min) or hepatic impairment (total bilirubin > 3 ULN and any AST value) on the pharmacokinetics of PFN are yet to be studied [6].

Therapeutics: PFN is used in the diagnosis of different cancer conditions. It is approved by the FDA for the diagnosis of conditions like ovarian cancer [9,10] and lung cancer [12,13]. It is still yet to be approved for conditions like Pituitary cancer [29], Gastric cancer [16], and Renal cancer [30] due to insufficient data available.

Indications

FDA has approved the use of PFN for the diagnosis of the following conditions -

- (a) **Ovarian cancer:** The FDA recommended dose of PFN is intravenous infusion of 0.025 mg/kg diluted in 250 ml of 5% dextrose injection, administered over 60 minutes via a dedicated infusion line, one to nine hours before surgery [1]. This procedure should be done after abstaining from folic acid or folate-containing drugs for 48 hours before PFN administration [3].
- (b) **Lung cancer:** Preoperative and intraoperative tumour labeling allow better resection in the presence of indistinct pulmonary nodules and poorly defined langour opacities of the abnormal lung parenchyma, thus improving surgical removal of the tumor [5,14]. FDA recommends a dose of 0.025mg/kg, administered 1 to 24 hours prior to surgery.

The use of PFN is yet to be approved under the following conditions:

- (a) **Gastric cancer:** There are limitations regarding staging techniques thus various intraoperative approaches like PFN to diagnose gastric tumours have been introduced [4]. Recent studies have highlighted the overexpression of FR α in over one-third of gastric adenocarcinomas, making near-infrared imaging with PFN an attractive approach for the surgical treatment of gastric malignancies. However, no clear data from clinical trials is available [17].
- (b) **Renal cancer:** It is shown that, in contrast to the above cancer, in renal cancer, FR α is very abundant in the healthy renal parenchyma (up to 100% expression on the apical surface of the proximal tubules, which provide physiological folate reabsorption), but less expressed in the renal tumor, which appears dark (10–30% staining), whereas the surrounding normal tissue fluoresces brightly [18].
- (c) **Pituitary tumors:** Pituitary cancer accounts for 10% of all intracranial cancers and has a high recurrence rate. Therefore, it is necessary to properly detect and identify tumours [19]. Recent studies have been conducted to approve PFN as an intraoperative agent for pituitary cancer. Recently, it was discovered that FR alpha receptors are present in nonfunctional pituitary adenomas but not in functional adenomas [20]. However, the study to be conducted was terminated.

Administration

The recommended dose of PFN is a single intravenous infusion of 0.025 mg/kg diluted in 250 ml of 5% dextrose injection, administered over 60 minutes via a dedicated infusion line, one to nine hours before surgery [1].

Safety Profile

The safety of PFN was evaluated in three open-label clinical trials, two of which were in patients with ovarian cancer (N=150 and N=44) and another study in patients with lung cancer (N=100). The adverse effects occurring in more than 1% of patients were nausea (15%), vomiting (5.8%), abdominal pain (2.7%), flushing (1.7%), dyspepsia (1%), chest discomfort (1%), pruritus (1%), and hypersensitivity (1%) [1].

Contraindications

No contraindications have been reported; however, PFN associated with the mechanism of action may cause severe harm in pregnant women, but there is no data to evaluate PFN-associated severe

birth defects, miscarriages, or other teratogenic effects. Safety and efficacy in pediatrics have not yet been established [6].

Warning and Precautions

Infusion-related reactions: Adverse reactions such as nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, skin flushing, dyspepsia, chest discomfort, and pruritus have been reported with PFN administration. The reactions usually occurred within 15 minutes of the start of the infusion. Treatment with antihistamines and/or antiemetics may be used. If an adverse reaction occurs during administration, the infusion may be discontinued and resumed after treatment of the adverse reactions [1].

Risk of misinterpretation: Errors may occur when using PFN during intraoperative fluorescence imaging to detect ovarian cancer, including false negative and false positive results. Non-fluorescent tissue in the surgical field does not exclude the presence of ovarian cancer. Fluorescence may also occur in noncancerous tissue, such as areas of the bowel, kidneys, lymph nodes, and inflamed tissues [1].

Toxicity to embryo and foetus: Due to its mechanism of action, PFN may cause harm to the foetus when administered to a pregnant woman. Women of reproductive age should be informed of the potential risk to the foetus. The pregnancy status of women should be checked prior to administration [1].

Risk of aggregation: Use of an incorrect diluent to prepare PFN infusion solution may result in aggregation of PFN, which may cause infusion reactions such as nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, or rash. Only 5% of dextrose injection and no other diluents should be used to prepare PFN infusion solution [1].

Drug-Drug Interactions

Co-administration of folate, folic acid, or folate-containing dietary supplements showed pharmacokinetic effects by decreasing the binding of PFN to folate receptors overexpressed on ovarian cancer cells and could decrease the detection of malignant lesions with PFN. Therefore, it is recommended that administration of folate, folic acid, or folate-containing dietary supplements be avoided within 48 hours prior to PFN administration [1].

Pharmacoeconomics

The price of Cytalux Intravenous (3.2mg/1.6 ml) is \$ 3,187.50 [6].

Approval Status:

Pafolacianine was approved by FDA on November 29, 2021 as an optical imaging agent used for intraoperative detection of malignant ovarian cancer [27].

Discussion

Pafolacianine (PFN) is an imaging agent approved by the FDA for the diagnosis of ovarian and lung cancer in the human body [3]. PFN binds specifically to folate receptor alpha (FR α), a membrane-bound glycoprotein receptor, upregulated more in the ovarian and lung cancer cells. PFN binds with an affinity of ~1 nM26 and gets internalized by receptor-mediated endocytosis, thereby accumulating in FR α -expressing malignant lesions [4]. It is a folate analog conjugated to a fluorescent dye in the near-infrared, thus aiding in optical imaging during the surgery by absorbing the light in the near-infrared and thus emitting fluorescence for diagnosis of positive cancer cells [28]. FR α receptor is also expressed in breast and gastric cancer cells. However, the extent of expression of FR α receptor is more in ovarian and lung cancer cells followed by breast cancer and gastric cancer cells. PFN showed better efficacy in

diagnosing ovarian and lung cancer cells due to greater expression of FR α receptors in these organs. However, PFN is in the pipeline for approval by regulatory authorities in breast, gastric, renal, and pituitary cancer cells in the human body, as preclinical studies have shown potential positive results in the diagnosis of these cancer cells [5].

The safety profile of PFN was studied in three open-label clinical trials involving patients who were suffering from ovarian and lung cancer. The results of clinical studies showed that few

patients reported side effects such as nausea (15%), vomiting (5.8%), abdominal pain (2.7%), flushing (1.7%), dyspepsia (1%), chest discomfort (1%), pruritus (1%), and hypersensitivity (1%) due to intravenous administration of PFN. In addition, these side effects may occur within 15 minutes of administering the drug. Hence, precautionary measures using anti-histaminic and/or antiemetic medications are necessary like any other diagnostic agents. The safety profile of PFN is not established in pregnant women [1]. Therefore, this drug is not to be administered in women of childbearing age and pregnancy. In addition, false positive results during the diagnosis of ovarian and lung cancer cells may be possible, which requires careful interpretation of the results especially while carrying out the surgery of the cancer area. Beyond this, there is limited data on the use of PFN in patients with severe renal and liver impairment.

CONCLUSION

Pafolacianine is an intraoperative imaging agent for the diagnosis of ovarian and lung cancer in the human body. It has shown rapid onset of action with better efficacy and safety profile while diagnosing ovarian and lung cancer cells. The most common side effects include dyspepsia, vomiting, nausea, abdominal pain, chest discomfort, skin redness, itching, and hypersensitivity.

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